

Pertamina RU II Dumai's CSR Strategy to Overcome Drug Abuse through Empowerment Program in Laksamanasub-District

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ABSTRACT : Laksamana Sub-district located in 2nd ring of Pertamina RU II Dumai operational area. In the last two years, a series of community development programs have been carried out in this district, as part of Pertamina RU II Dumai's commitment to participate in overcoming social problems. However, drug abuse is not a simple problem. There are many parties who have interests, especially from local government such as the BNN, BKKBN and Detention Centre. This study focuses on Pertamina RU II Dumai's CSR strategy to deal with rampant drug abuse in Dumai City generally, especially LaksamanaSub-district through a multi-stakeholder approach. As a result, premier and tertiary interventions were carried out on vulnerable groups such as children, youth, housewives and even former drug abusers. Meanwhile, CSR programs are synergized with local government and community groups programs. These programs focus on (1) developing child-friendly open spaces, (2) increasing education through reading corners, (3) increasing the competence of prisoners, (4) and developing economic center.

KEYWORDS -corporate social responsibility, drug abuse, empowerment

I. INTRODUCTION

Drug abuse in Indonesia has become a national disaster [1]. Potential losses due to drug abuse are estimated at 74.4 trillion rupiah [2]. These losses include costs incurred for the justice system, health care and rehabilitation, loss of productivity, and environmental damage [3]. Therefore, drug abuse requires attention from various parties. Not only the government and the community, but also the private sector through CSR programs.

Dumai City is a red zone for drug abuse in Riau [4]—a province with the 9th highest drug cases in Indonesia [5]. This city one of popular gateways for drug distribution in Riau province [6]. The drugs are smuggled from Malaysia and Singapore by sea to the port in LaksamanaSub-district. In this sub-district, drug abuses has become daily activity. Drug consumption and transactions are carried out openly; a father forces his son to sell drugs [7], and many children neglected because their parents were imprisoned.

Table 1. 10 Province with the Highest Prevalence of Drug Abuse in Indonesia (2017)

No.	PROVINCE	POPULATION	CASE	%	LOSS(IDRM)
1.	DKI Jakarta	7,800,600	260,656	3.34%	6,538,644
2.	North Sumatra	10,137,500	256,657	2.53%	6,438,332
3.	East Kalimantan	2,071,436	43,911	2.12%	1,101,512
4.	Jambi	2,626,200	53,177	2.02%	1,333,954
5.	Central Kalimantan	1,967,200	38,981	1.98%	977,858
6.	South Kalimantan	3,025,600	59,590	1.97%	1,494,835
7.	South Sulawesi	6,237,800	121,366	1.95%	3,044,516
8.	Lampung	6,028,700	116,845	1.94%	2,931,090
9.	Riau	4,893,700	91,415	1.87%	2,293,170
10.	Banten	9,296,400	170,444	1.83%	4,275,649

TOTAL	54,085,136	1,213,042	2.24%	30,429,560
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Source: Processed data from "BNN National Survey"

National Narcotics Agency (BNN), Regional Police (Polda), Navy Military Police (Pomal) and Indonesian National Army (TNI) have formed a team to tackle drug abuse. Many perpetrators have been arrested and put on trial, one of which is the chairman of neighborhood association, who was arrested while trying to smuggle 50 kilograms of shabu-shabu from Malaysia [8]. However, new actors continue to emerge, making drug abuse in the Laksamana Sub-district seem never ending. Therefore, a comprehensive strategy is needed to overcome the problem of drug abuse. Not only focusing on arrests and repressive interventions, but also taking an approach through a more preventive and proactive strategy.

Geographically, Laksamana Sub-district is located in 2nd ring of Pertamina RU II Dumai operational area. Even though the area is not a priority for CSR implementation, Pertamina RU II Dumai has a commitment to participate in overcoming this very destructive national disaster. This is realized by implementing a series of CSR programs that have been started in 2019. This study focuses on finding out the CSR strategy to overcome drug abuse in Laksamana Sub-district, Dumai Kota.

Interestingly, Laksamana Sub-district natural resources has is potential for eco-tourism that has not been optimized. There are stretches of mangroves located at RT 3 and RT 7¹. There is also a port that can be used as an entry point for many tourists in the future. It is important, because all the potential that exists can be wasted because of the impact of drug abuse that is not handled properly.

II. FRAMEWORK

Drug abuse has a holistic aspect because it impacts biologically, emotionally, psychologically, and spiritually[9]. Therefore, the rehabilitation procedure for drug users must also use a holistic approach [10]. The approach referred to is not only limited to efforts to eliminate user addiction from various aspects, but also includes multi-stakeholder involvement [11]. Even so, the approach that has been mentioned tends to be repressive because it only deals with the local and personal scope [12]. Meanwhile, drug trafficking has yet to

Figure 1. Drug Abuse and Possible Interventions to Address

Source: Elaborated Theoretic Study

be resolved, which makes community feel uneasy. The economic condition and the presence of dealers and other drug users in an environment can make a rehabilitated person repeat his mistakes again [13].

Therefore, personal and repressive approaches are no longer sufficient to deal with drug abuse problems in the red zone as happened in Laksamana Sub-district. Need an intervention from various aspects to create a conducive environment. These interventions can be categorized into primary, secondary and tertiary [14]. Primary intervention serves to prevent, while secondary intervention serves to restore the user's

condition right away. Meanwhile, tertiary intervention is an advanced stage of the rehabilitation process. To facilitate all these efforts, multi-stakeholder participation is needed as a macro perspective.

III. METHODS

This study used a descriptive qualitative method with in-depth interviews and literature review as a research instrument. The research was carried out in a participatory way by providing assistance on every process or stages of the program. To obtain, process and analyze data, a multi-stakeholder approach is used. The unit of

¹ An administrative division covering a small area in a district or sub-district.

analysis of this study is a representative of the parties involved in efforts to deal with drug abuse in the Laksamana Sub-district.

Informants were selected purposively by considering their capabilities to answer questions. The informants of this research include the Unit Manager of Pertamina's CSR RU II Dumai, Head of the Laksamana Sub-district, Head of Class IIB Dumai Detention Center (Rutan), Head of BNN Dumai, Kampung KB Keberkahan Bersama members, local heroes and CSR beneficiaries. The data that has been collected are then categorized, analyzed and re-examined to reach a conclusion.

IV. DISCUSSION

Pertamina RU II Dumai seeks to holistically address the problem of drug abuse in Laksamana Sub-district. However, the scope of the work was too broad to be done on a limited budget. In addition, there are parties both from the government and local communities who are already involved in drug eradication efforts. Therefore, the strategy carried out by Pertamina RU II Dumai is to synergize with various existing parties such as the local government, the National Population and Family Planning Board (BKKBN), BNN, Class IIB Dumai Detention Center (Rutan), Vocational Training Centers (BLK) and community groups.

Figure 2. Coordination between Pertamina RU II Dumai, Local Government, BKKBN, DPPP, Kampung KB and BNN
 Source: Researcher's documentation

Synergy is carried out with the aim that the functions of each institution do not collide with one another. BNN has the authority to conduct investigations and arrests of drug abuse cases. The Ministry of Law and Human Rights is responsible for carrying out recovery on physical, psychological, emotional and spiritual impacts through detention centers and rehabilitation installations. Meanwhile the BKKBN and Ministry of Women and Child Empowerment (PPPA) demonstrated their intervention through preventive action. That way, Pertamina RU II Dumai has the opportunity to create synergy with its CSR programs that are categorized into primary and tertiary interventions.

Table 2. Multi-stakeholder Intervention in Efforts to Eradicate Drug Abuse in Laksamana Sub-district

Intervention	Primary	Secondary	Tertiary
Local Government	• Implement road closure and curfew regulations	• Coordinating arrest procedures with local police	-
Pertamina RU II Dumai	• Child-friendly open spaces development • Improving education through reading corner • Economic centers development	-	Upgrading Prisoners' Competencies
BKKBN	• Initiation of MSMEs groups to improve family welfare • Anti-drug socialization & campaign	-	-
BNN	• Anti-drug socialization & campaign • Conduct an investigation	• Coordinating arrest procedures with local police	• Provide assistance in recovery and rehabilitation
Rutan	-	• Provide assistance to detainees prior to trial	• Provide social and religious assistance

Source: Processed premier data

This is because the parties that have been mentioned have their own programs, so the intended synergy demands Pertamina RU II Dumai to design programs that can complement or support existing programs. In the

process, a series of programs are designed to focus on developing open spaces, improving youth education through reading corners, increasing the competence of prisoners, and developing economic centers. These programs are focused on vulnerable groups in Laksamana Sub-district. Including children and youth, housewives, even groups of prisoners or former drug dealers.

Source: Researcher's documentation

IV.1. Child-friendly Open Space Development

Children are the most vulnerable group in Laksamana Sub-district. Bad environment will affect the child's personality maturity [15]. As a result, they will end up like adults in that environment; drug user or dealer. In order to provide a good environment for growing children, Pertamina RU II Dumai conduct a collaboration with the local government and Kampung KB Keberkahan Bersam to build child-friendly open spaces. This concept is manifested in the form of a playground with various attraction. Apart from the playground, there is also a gazebo which is used for productive activities such as posyandu² cadre meetings and various trainings. That way parents can directly supervise their children without losing productivity.

The purpose of developing open spaces is to create a crowd point that will narrow the space for drug abuse. This is because one of the factors that made the transactions in Laksamana Sub-district happen was the lack of supervision. By providing open space and providing access for the crowd, the transaction process can be minimized. So the children have

a more safe space for their developing period.

IV.2. Improving Education Through Reading Corner

Apart from providing an open space to play, children are also encouraged to do more productive activities by reading books. This activity is carried out by providing a reading corner along with the books and educational games. Some of these books were provided by Pertamina RU II Dumai, some were obtained through donations from various parties.

The provision of a reading corner aims to familiarize children with educational activities, in line with efforts to divert children's attention from negative environments. The existence of a reading corner is expected to stimulate children's interest in education. The strategy is based on the assumption that drug abusers have an average level of

Figure 4. "Bahtera" Reading Corner

Source: Researcher's documentation

secondary education and below [16].

IV.3. Upgrading Prisoner's Competencies

One of the factors for the large number of drug dealers in Laksamana Sub-district is the lack of jobs to support themselves. Although the legal procedures imposed on drug users and traffickers are quite heavy, they are not sufficient enough to eliminate this profession in Laksamana Sub-district. Especially when the access to get a job becomes lower after being caught in a legal case. This is due to the stigma that society gives to prisoners, so that both dealers and users are rarely accepted to work in society. At this stage, ex-convicts who have been involved with drugs both as dealers and users are defined as part of the vulnerable group. Those who do not have a variety of

Figure 5. Aquaponic Instalation Framing in Detention Centre Dumai

Source: Researcher's documentation

²Community Based Health Effort (UKBM) implemented by, from and with the community, to empower and provide convenience to the community to obtain health services for mothers, infants and children under five.

skills will easily return to the profession that sent him to prison.

Therefore, in order to provide more job options for ex-convicts, Pertamina RU II Dumai collaborates with the Work Training Center (BLK) to conduct training for inmates who have served at least 1/3 of the detention period. In addition, Pertamina RU II Dumai also provided equipment that the prisoners could use interchangeably and sell their products to external parties. Part of the income will be allocated as capital so that economic activities in the detention center can be sustainable, while the rest will be distributed to the prisoners who work. During the period of detention, it is possible for the prisoners to get savings from the produce. So that when it comes time to leave the detention center, they have enough savings to open small businesses or open medium-scale job opportunities.

IV.4. Economic Center Development

One of the factors that makes drug trafficking so rampant in Indonesia is that drug sales offer huge returns in an instant way [17]. This makes efforts to increase the capacity of former drug abusers while encouraging them to engage in a more modest sector of employment sound futile. However, that does not mean it is impossible to do. One of these efforts is realized by creating an economic driver that involves a lot of labor.

Laksamana Sub-district has mangrove areas that are very potential to be developed as eco-tourism. However, this effort does not only require involvement, but also institutional readiness. The lack of public awareness of the environment and the risk of asset misuses are factors that must be carefully considered. Therefore, establishing an economic center is the first step towards developing an eco-tourism area in the future. The focus of this program is to rebrand³Laksamana Sub-district through its signature products. These products are produced by Kampung KB Keberkahan Bersama, a community consisting of MSMEs in Laksamana Sub-district. This community is expected to raise funds independently to develop eco-tourism areas even without additional support from Pertamina RU II Dumai.

Even though the MSMEs involved were mostly elderly women, their persistence was able to encourage the youth, who later established themselves as UPPKA⁴Pandawa, an MSMEs engaged in screen printing. Apart from these groups, the economic center development strategy is expected to stimulate new group emergence consisting more youth in order to drive the economy of Laksamana Sub-district community.

V. CONCLUSION

In order to overcome the problem of drug abuse and its impact in Laksamana Sub-district, Pertamina RU II Dumai conduct primary and tertiary interventions through a series of empowerment programs for vulnerable groups. The groups include children, youth, housewives and even former drug users. This is done by collaborating with multi-stakeholders such as the local government, BKKBN, BNN, detention centers, BLKs and community groups. The

strategic CSR programs carried out by Pertamina RU II Dumai includes:

1. Developing child-friendly open spaces through a playground. The focus of this strategy is to create a crowd spot, so that the supervisory function can run by involving various parties, apart from the parents of children who are active in the same environment.
2. Improving children's education through the reading corner. With the existence of literacy sources, it is hoped that the attention of children and adolescents can be diverted to positive and productive activities.
3. Improving the competence of prisoners. The focus of this program is to provide provisions and

Production Process in Laksamana Sub-district
Source: Researcher's documentation

³Laksamana Sub-district is well known for its massive drug trafficking. One of its favourite area is known as Kampung Dalam.

⁴Community groups legally supported by the National Population and Family Planning Board (BKKBN) to increase family income and welfare.

competencies for prisoners, especially prisoners with drug abuse cases. Former drug users or dealers are not only provided with skills through training, but also savings from selling the products they produce during their detention period. So they can open a small business when their detention is over.

4. Developing economic centers is not only to improve the economy of the beneficiaries, but also as a foundation in developing Laksamana Sub-district as a tourist area. With the existence of a tourist area that begins with the success of an economic center, this program is expected to create new groups that will contribute to empowerment and minimize cases of drug abuse in society.

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